

BARCELONA DECLARATION ON OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

RINN ORI summer event - workshop Sustainability

Bianca Kramer

2026-09-23

<https://tinyurl.com/rinn-20260623-sustainability>

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information

BARCELONA
DECLARATION ON
OPEN RESEARCH
INFORMATION

Commitment 1

We will make openness
the default for the
research information
we use and produce

BARCELONA
DECLARATION ON
OPEN RESEARCH
INFORMATION

Commitment 2

We will work with
services and systems
that support and
enable open research
information

BARCELONA
DECLARATION ON
OPEN RESEARCH
INFORMATION

Commitment 3

We will support the
sustainability of
infrastructures
for open research
information

BARCELONA
DECLARATION ON
OPEN RESEARCH
INFORMATION

Commitment 4

We will support collective
action to accelerate the
transition to openness of
research information

BARCELONA
DECLARATION ON
OPEN RESEARCH
INFORMATION

Commitment 3

We will support the
sustainability of
infrastructures
for open research
information

Sustainability

Funding, governance, and community engagement needed for long-term reliable operation.

Barcelona Declaration - Commitment 3

3

We will support the sustainability of infrastructures for open research information

- We take responsibility for supporting infrastructures for open research information, for instance by participating in community building and community governance and by providing fair and equitable contributions to the financial stability and development of these infrastructures.
- We expect the infrastructures that we support to implement good practices for community governance and sustainability (e.g., Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure).

Agenda

1. Currently supported infrastructures and the models they use
2. Choices for institutions - what's important to you?
3. Examples: OpenAlex / OpenAIRE institutional memberships
4. Sustainability at system level

Infrastructures and sustainability models

Image adapted from Barcelona: Casas Rocamora by Ludvig14, CC-BY-SA 3.0

Examples of open infrastructures for research information

Currently supported infrastructures

What open infrastructures for research information does your organization:

1. Support **financially** ?
2. Support through participation in **governance** ?
3. Support through **community engagement** (contributing code, data, curation) ?

Financial sustainability models

- Institutional contributions
- Membership model
- Grants / project funding
- Host institution support
- Service revenue (mission-consistent)
- Subscriptions
- Donations
- Partnerships
- Other: _____

What model(s) do the infrastructures mentioned use ?

Financial sustainability models

Institutional contributions

Grants / Project funding

Host institution support

Membership model

Service revenue

Other, ...

What model(s) do the infrastructures mentioned use ?

name infrastructure

€ = financial support

 = governance

 = community engagement / contributions

I = inst. contributions

M = membership

F = project funding

S = service revenue

H = inst. hosting

O = other

OpenAIRE

€

F
M
S

OpenAlex

€ (

F
M
S

(SCOSS)

€

I

Crossref

€

M

DSpace

€

I
M
H

ORCID

€

M

ROR

I
F

€ = financial support
 = governance
 = community engagement / contributions

Choices for institutions

Image adapted from Barcelona: Casas Rocamora by Ludvig14, CC-BY-SA 3.0

Choices for institutions - what's important to you?

1. **Why** does (or would) your institution decide to support open infrastructures ?
2. **How** does (or could) your institution support open infrastructures?
3. What **barrier(s)** does your institution face in supporting open infrastructures?

Choices for institutions - what's important to you?

1. **Why** does (or would) your institution decide to support open infrastructures ?
2. **How** does (or could) your institution support open infrastructures?
3. What **barrier(s)** does your institution face in supporting open infrastructures?

Choices for institutions - what's important to you?

-

- What **information / financial models** would be useful for institutions ?
- Are institutions prepared to **reinvest money** saved on cancellation of closed solutions ?

Concrete examples

Concrete examples - OpenAlex

Member

\$5k/year

For institutions committed to open research

- ✓ **Admin dashboard**
OpenAlex usage data for your institution
- ✓ **Affiliation editor**
Curate author affiliations (training resources provided)
- ✓ **Unsub access**
Data-driven journal subscription decisions
- ✓ **Nomination rights**
For our Community Advisory Board
- ✓ **Quarterly meetings**
With the product team

[Become a Member](#)

Most Popular

Member+

\$10k/year

For Members using lots of OpenAlex data

- ✓ **Everything in Member**
- ✓ **1 million API credits/day**
On a single API key
- ✓ **Data Sync Service**
Get changes in the data every day

[Get Member+](#)

Partner

\$20k+/year

For institutions driving open infrastructure

- ✓ **Everything in Member+**
- ✓ **5 high-usage researcher accounts**
Give select researchers at your institution extra-high API limits
- ✓ **5hr consulting/year**
Custom integrations, analysis, or training

[Become a Partner](#)

Concrete examples - OpenAIRE

NL Research Portal:

€ 10.000 + € 14.500 0.1 fte

OpenAIRE membership:

€ 1.500 / year

Met dit lidmaatschap:

- draagt uw instelling actief bij aan de duurzame inbedding van een Europese Open Science Infrastructuur,
- verkrijgt u invloed op beleid en governance van OpenAIRE,
- kunt u de ontwikkelroadmap van de NL Research Portal mede vormgeven,
- ontvangt u 30% korting op alle OpenAIRE-diensten.

OpenAIRE services (fee)

OpenAIRE Metadata Validator

"Check repository compliance with OpenAIRE"

The OpenAIRE Metadata Validator is a service that checks a repository's compliance with OpenAIRE, for repository managers, by validating it against the OpenAIRE guidelines.

Users: **Content & service providers**

Pricing: **On Demand**

OpenAIRE MONITOR

"Personalised research monitoring"

OpenAIRE MONITOR is a service that produces well-documented, timely and accurate monitoring indicators of research activities for funders, research initiatives and organisations, by creating personalised and on...

Users: **Funders & policy makers, Research Performing Organisations, Research Infrastructures**

Pricing: **MONITOR Standard**

OpenAIRE CONNECT

"Custom, on demand, scientific gateways"

The CONNECT Dashboard is a platform as a service that enables institutions, universities, or lead teams on a scientific domain, to easily create, configure and manage, their own customised web portal that...

Users: **Researchers, Research Performing Organisations, Research Infrastructures**

Pricing: **CONNECT Standard**

OpenAIRE PROVIDE

"One-stop shop for sharing, improving, and enriching your content"

OpenAIRE PROVIDE is the scholarly gateway that receives content registration requests and provides guidance for content providers by viewing a personalised, user-friendly dashboard that shows the necessar...

Users: **Content & service providers, Research Performing Organisations, Research Infrastructures**

Pricing: **On demand**

<https://catalogue.openaire.eu/>

And how about ?

Dimensions

A model for thinking about innovation

<https://www.digital-science.com/blog/2024/05/barcelona-a-beautiful-horizon/>

And how about ?

ACM DIGITAL
LIBRARY

ACM Digital Library: Evolving Access to Support Open Research

As ACM advances its commitment to Open Access, we are evolving our licensing model to better support both accessibility and sustainability. To support this shift, ACM is introducing two levels of access - **Digital Library Premium** and **Digital Library Basic** - designed to balance our mission of openness with the need to maintain a world-class publishing program.

<https://libraries.acm.org/subscriptions-access/academic/dl-pricing>

Sustainability at system level

Image adapted from Barcelona: Casas Rocamora by Ludvig14, CC-BY-SA 3.0

Sustainability at system level

- How does support for individual infrastructures support the wider ecosystem of open research information ? (for NL and broader)
- What role can SURF / UKB / UNL / SHB / OpenScience NL play ?
 - Infrastructure call (BROCCOLI, DURF, MORIS and more)
 - Strategisch Plan Integrale Infrastructuur voor Open Science (SPII)

System level initiatives

**Invest in Open
Infrastructure**

- Infrafinder
- IOI Network fund
- Focus on governance & capacity

- Evaluating & selecting infrastructures
- Promote and facilitate (consortial) funding
- Focus on ecosystem

- Making infrastructure support visible
- Highlight supporting institutions

The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure

Governance

- **Coverage across the scholarly enterprise** – research transcends disciplines, geography, institutions, and stakeholders. Organisations and the infrastructure they run need to reflect this.
- **Stakeholder governed** – a board-governed organisation drawn from the stakeholder community builds confidence that the organisation will make decisions driven by community consensus and a balance of interests.
- **Non-discriminatory participation or membership** – we see the best option to be an “opt-in” approach with principles of non-discrimination and inclusivity, where any relevant group may express an interest and should be welcome. Representation in governance must reflect the character of the community or membership.
- **Transparent governance** – to foster trust, the processes and policies for

Governance

- Coverage across the scholarly enterprise
- Stakeholder governed
- Non-discriminatory participation or membership
- Transparent governance
- Cannot lobby
- Living will
- Regular review of purpose and community value

Sustainability

- Transparent operations
- Time-limited funds are used only for time-limited activities
- Goal to generate surplus
- Establish and maintain financial reserves guided by policy
- Mission-consistent revenue generation
- Revenue generated from services, not data
- Volunteer labour
- Transition planning

Sustainability

- **Transparent operations** – to enable organisational accountability and openness, the operating policies and procedures, detailed financials, sustainability models, fees, strategic and product roadmaps, organisational charts, and other appropriate operational information should be made openly available (within the constraints of privacy laws). Information should be available for investigation and reuse by the community.
- **Time-limited funds are used only for time-limited activities** – operations should be supported by sustainable revenue sources, whereas time-limited funds are used only for time-limited activities. Depending on grants to fund ongoing and/or long-term operations fully makes organisations fragile and distracts from maintaining core infrastructure.
- **Goal to generate surplus** – it is not enough to merely survive; organisations and services have to be able to adapt and change. Organisations and services that

System level initiatives

Sustainability at system level

- How does support for individual infrastructures support the wider ecosystem of open research information ? (for NL and broader)
- What role can SURF / UKB / UNL / SHB / OpenScience NL play ?
 - Infrastructure call (BROCCOLI, DURF, MORIS and more)
 - Strategisch Plan Integrale Infrastructuur voor Open Science (SPII)